

EMPLOYERS SERVICE QUALITY AND ENGINEER'S PERFORMANCE IN ENGINEERING FIRMS IN TRANS-AMADI INDUSTRIAL LAYOUT, PORT HARCOURT, RIVERS STATE

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Abstract: This study examined the influence of employer service quality on engineers' performance in selected engineering firms located in the Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, it investigated how four dimensions of employer service quality namely: communication, welfare, training, and workplace safety affect engineers' performance. The study focused on engineers working in engineering firms within the Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout. A sample of 50 engineers was drawn using random sampling methods to capture insights from employees directly involved in technical and operational functions. A quantitative survey design was employed. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed from validated scales in organizational management and engineering management literature. The instrument captured demographic variables, perceptions of employer practices, and self-reported performance measures. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multiple regression modeling, carried out using SPSS software. The results showed that employer service quality has a significant influence on engineers' performance. Training ($\beta = 0.33$, $p < .01$) and workplace safety ($\beta = 0.41$, $p < .01$) were statistically significant predictors of performance, while communication and welfare, though positively associated, were not significant predictors. The regression model explained approximately 38.4% of the variance in engineers' performance. These findings highlight that technical competence enhancement and safe work environments are the strongest performance drivers in engineering firms within industrial hubs. Recommendations were made on strategies that firms can adopt to enhance employer service quality and thereby improve engineers' performance.

Keywords: Employer Service Quality, Engineers' Performance, Training, Workplace Safety, Engineering Management, Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout, Nigeria

Introduction

In today's world, effective management of employer service quality and engineer's performance has become more critical than ever in engineering environment [1]. Engineering firms are central to infrastructure, industrial development, and technological innovation in developing countries including, Nigeria. In industrial zones such as Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout, Port Harcourt, these firms employ engineers whose performance, productivity, and commitment determine project success, safety, and competitiveness. The way in which

employers treat engineers through communication, welfare, training, work safety, feedback, recognition, and support constitutes what can be regarded as employer service quality. Employer service quality is increasingly recognized as a critical managerial factor influencing job satisfaction, performance, and retention of employees. Studies in Rivers State have indicated that safety training and health and safety practices positively affect employee performance in oil and gas companies [2].

Similarly, welfare provisions such as safety measures, insurance, and vacation policy have been shown to be significantly associated with organizational effectiveness in oil and gas firms in Bonny Island [3]. Meanwhile, work environment dimensions such as physical conditions, feedback, management practices, and safety have been found to influence performance in hospitality and construction firms in Port Harcourt [4][5].

Despite these previous findings, many engineering firms, especially in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout still face challenges including inadequate welfare packages, poor safety culture, limited training, insufficient feedback, and weak employer-employee relations, while, little empirical research has focused specifically on engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout. The specific ways in which employer service quality components (communication, safety, training, welfare, feedback) affect engineers' performance in this context have not been clearly established. Without this knowledge, firms may continue suboptimal practices, leading to underutilization of engineers' potential with associated issues such as: reduction of engineers' motivation, diminish innovation, increase absenteeism, and degrade performance and productivity. Therefore, there is need to investigate the resultant effect of improved employer service quality on the engineer's performance in engineering firm in Trans-Amadi Industrial layout. Hence, this study examines how employer service quality relates to engineers' performance in engineering firms situated in this specific industrial area.

Research Questions

1. How does employer communication and feedback affect engineers' job performance in engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout?
2. What influence do welfare and motivation packages have on engineers' productivity in these firms?
3. To what extent do training and career development opportunities affect engineers' effectiveness?
4. How do workplace safety practices influence engineers' performance in Trans-Amadi engineering firms?
5. What strategies can firms adopt to enhance employer service quality and thereby improve engineer performance?

Research Hypotheses

The study will test the following hypotheses:

H₀: Employers service quality have no significant relationship with engineers' performance in engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

H₁: Employers service quality have a significant relationship with engineers' performance in engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout

H₂₀: Employer communication and feedback have no significant effect on engineers' performance in engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

H₂: Employer communication and feedback have significant effect on engineers' performance in engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

H₃₀: Welfare and motivation packages have no significant effect on engineers' productivity in engineering firms situated in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

H3: Welfare and motivation packages have significant effect on engineers' productivity in engineering firms situated in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

H40: Training and career development opportunities have no significant impact on engineers' effectiveness in engineering firms located in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

H4: Training and career development opportunities have significant impact on engineers' effectiveness in engineering firms located in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

H50: Workplace safety practices have no significant influence on engineers' performance in engineering firms sited in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

H5: Workplace safety practices have significant influence on engineers' performance in engineering firms sited in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

Significance of the Research

This study will be significant in the following ways:

Engineering Firms: The findings will provide insights into how employer service quality influences engineers' performance, thereby helping management design human resource policies to improve productivity, reduce turnover, and boost competitiveness.

Engineers: The study will highlight key aspects of employer service quality that affect their performance, enabling advocacy for better working conditions.

Policy Makers and Professional Associations: Institutions such as the Nigerian Society of Engineers (NSE) and Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN) can use the findings to strengthen policies promoting fair treatment, safety, and professional development.

Researchers and Scholars: The study will contribute to literature in Engineering Management, offering a case study of employer–employee relations in an industrial cluster of Port Harcourt.

Literature Review

Review of Related Works

Some of the studies of growing body of empirical study from supports links between employer practices and employee outcomes include:

In the study by [6], the safety training, safety behavior and safety performance in selected oil and gas companies in Niger delta was modeled. Safety training was segregated into teaching and practical safety trainings. Structured questionnaire, designed based on 5-point Likert scale, was used for data collection; Pearson correlation, regression and t-test were used for the analyses. The Pearson coefficient of the correlation analysis results revealed that the relationship between Teaching-based Safety Training and Practical-based Safety It was concluded that safety training has significant impact on safety behavior and safety performance. It was recommended that management of oil and gas firms should utilize complete safety training package in order to enhance both safety behavior and safety performance of their workers.

In the propose study by [3], they investigated welfare packages in oil and gas firms in Bonny Island (Rivers State) and reported significant positive associations between welfare provisions (insurance, vacation policy, workplace safety) and organizational effectiveness

In the research carried out by [4], they examined hospitality firms in Port Harcourt and found that physical work environment and supervisor support significantly predicted employee performance. Their results obtained emphasize the importance of managerial communication and ergonomic workspaces in enhancing productivity.

In the study by [7], they investigated safety management and job performance among employees in manufacturing firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Using a survey design with a sample drawn from 16 selected manufacturing firms, they reported significant relationships between supervision and monitoring and employee work output, between management commitment and timely delivery, and between transparency and innovativeness. The authors recommend institutionalizing emergency plans, first-aid facilities, regular safety training, and periodic safety audits as practical measures to improve job performance.

[8], in his study examined the impact of Quality Work-Life Programs (QWLFP) on organizational commitment in Benin City’s manufacturing sector. A stratified cross-sectional survey and regression analysis was adopted. The outcomes of the study show that QWL programs including flexible schedules, career development, and health/wellness benefits are positively associated with higher organizational commitment. The study offers practical recommendations for tailoring QWL interventions to local socio-demographic needs and includes a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for the published version, making it a suitable, fully citable replacement for region-specific work on interactive management practices and QWL.

Several recent policy briefs and empirical papers by [9], underline how employee motivation, career development, and non-monetary recognition increase job satisfaction and productivity among workers in Rivers State sectors such as construction and manufacturing.

Conceptual Model

The conceptual model positions Employer Service Quality (with four dimensions) as the independent variable influencing Engineers' Performance (productivity, effectiveness, innovation, safety compliance). Firm size, sector (electrical, mechanical, electronics), and engineers' experience are treated as control variables.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model Showing Relationship between Employer Service Quality and Engineers' Performance.

Methodology

The methods and techniques used for testing and examined the data collected, and evaluation of the results found was explained in detailed. This study adopted a quantitative survey research design. A sample size of 50 engineers was selected using simple random sampling, this size was deemed adequate for testing and empirical demonstration. The selection ensured representation across firms in the industrial layout. Based on the recommendation by the company’s management, questionnaires were administered to staff (engineers) of 10 private engineering companies within Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout, Port Harcourt. Structured questionnaires were administered to 5 engineers each in the 10 selected firms, making it a total of 50 respondents (engineers) to collect data in order to examine the effect of employer service quality on engineers’ performance in engineering firms within the chosen industrial area.

Statistical methods such as descriptive, correlation, and regression analyses embedded in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 25.0 were applied to test the relationships among variables. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to summarize the data. Correlation analysis was employed to examine associations among variables, while regression analysis was used to test the predictive effect of employer service quality on engineers' performance. Validity was ensured through expert review by practitioners in engineering management. Reliability was assessed through internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha.

A 5- point Likert scale of 1 to 5 in questionnaire was adopted to assess the degree of agreement of each parameters (Communication, welfare, Training and Safety), where '1' represented strongly disagree, '2' disagree, '3' undecided, '4' strongly agree and '5' strongly agree. Engineers' performance was measured on a 7-point composite scale where '1' represented very poor, '2' poor, '3' fair, '4' moderate, '5' good, '6' very good, and '7' excellent.

Equations Used for Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics summarize the central tendency and variability of the data collected from the field survey. The key measures include:

$$\text{Mean} = \bar{X} = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \quad (1)$$

Where:

- X = sample mean
- X_i = sample mean
- n = total number of observations

Standard deviation (SD) is given as:

$$\text{SD} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2}{n - 1}} \quad (2)$$

Variance is given as:

$$\text{Var}(x) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2}{n - 1} \quad (3)$$

Pearson's correlation coefficient, r is given as:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}} \quad (4)$$

Where:

- r_{xy} = Pearson's correlation coefficient between variable x and y.
- X_i, Y_i = individual data points
- X, Y = means of x and y

Regression was applied to test the predictive influence of employer service quality dimensions on engineers' performance. The general multiple regression model is given as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

Where:

Y = Engineer's performance (dependent variable)

X₁ = Communication

X₂ = Welfare

X₃ = Training

X₄ = Safety

β₀ = Constant(Intercept)

β₁, β₂, β₃, β₄ = Regression coefficient

Coefficient of determination (R²) is given as:

$$R^2 = \frac{SSR}{SST} = 1 - \frac{SSE}{SST} \quad (6)$$

Where:

SSR = Regression sum of squares

SSE = Error sum of squares

SST = Total sum of squares

F- test for overall significance is given as:

$$F = \frac{MSR}{MSE} = \frac{SSR / K}{SSE / (n - k - 1)} \quad (7)$$

Where:

k = Number of independent variables

n = Sample size

MSR = Mean square regression

MSE = Mean square error

t- test for individual predictors is given as :

$$t = \frac{b_i}{SE(b_i)} \quad (8)$$

b_i = Estimated regression coefficient for predictor X_i

SE(b_i) = Standard error of the coefficient

Mathematical equations 1 to 8 cover all required by SPSS for the analyses and overall model fit

Results and Discussion

The results of the data collected from engineers in selected engineering firms within the Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The analysis is structured to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses formulated. Data are presented through descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analyses.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of respondents, the sample is dominated by male engineers (76%), reflecting the male-dominated nature of the engineering profession in Nigeria [10]. The majority (60%) hold a

Bachelor of Engineering degree, and most respondents fall within the age range of 31–40 years (40%). This indicates a relatively youthful and experienced workforce.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents (n = 50)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	38	76.0
	Female	12	24.0
Age	21–30 years	14	28.0
	31–40 years	20	40.0
	41–50 years	10	20.0
	Above 50 years	6	12.0
Education Level	B.Eng	30	60.0
	HND	12	24.0
	M.Eng/PhD	8	16.0
Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	15	30.0
	6–10 years	20	40.0
	Above 10 years	15	30.0

Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

Table 2 depicts the descriptive statistics of variables. While Figure 2 and Figure 3 shows bar chart illustrate the aggregate mean scores of the constructs measured on the 5-point Likert scale and engineers' Performance measured with a 7-point composite scale respectively. The results show that for constructs measured on the 5-point Likert scale, most respondents leaned towards 'Agree' and 'Strongly Agree,' reflecting moderate satisfaction with employer service quality. Communication (Mean = 3.70) received the highest score, followed closely by Welfare (3.58), Training (3.56), and Safety (3.48).

Safety recorded the lowest score, indicating an area that requires management attention. Engineers' Performance, measured with a 7-point composite scale, had a mean score of 5.03. This reflects self-reported performance levels between 'Good' and 'Very Good.' The higher scale allowed for more refined differences in performance, suggesting that while employer service quality practices are only moderately satisfactory, engineers maintain relatively high performance due to professional commitment and adaptive

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation
Communication	3.70	0.68
Welfare	3.58	0.72
Training	3.56	0.74
Safety	3.48	0.70
Performance	5.03	1.10

Mean Scores of Employer Service Quality Dimensions (5-point scale)

Figure 2: Mean Scores of Employer Service Quality Dimensions (5 Point Scale)

Figure 3: Engineers' Performance (7-Point Scale Composite)

Correlation Analysis Results and Correlation Testing on Hypotheses

Table 3 and Table 4 show correlation matrix and correlation testing on hypotheses of the study. From Table 3, it is observed that Training ($r = 0.55, p < 0.01$) and safety ($r = 0.59, p < 0.01$) are significantly correlated with performance, indicating that firms investing in training and workplace safety are likely to improve engineers’ performance. For communication ($r = 0.32, p < 0.01$) and welfare ($r = 0.28, p < 0.01$) are significantly correlated with performance, meaning that as effective communication from employer increases, engineers’ performance also tends to improve, and welfare policies (like salaries, benefits, health support) are linked to better performance.

From Table 4 it is easily observed that the Pearson r value is greater than 0.000 for all the hypotheses mentioned above, which indicates that there is positive correlation between employer service quality as calculate via selected factors and engineers’ performance. The results proves the significance in relationship of employee service quality factors chosen (Communication, welfare, training, and safety) for this study to the engineers’ performances at work

Table 3: Correlation Matrix of Employer Service Quality Dimensions and Engineers’ Performance

Variable	Comm.	Welfare	Training	Safety	Perf.
Communication	1	0.41	0.38	0.29	0.32
Welfare		1	0.44	0.35	0.28
Training			1	0.51	0.55
Safety				1	0.59
Performance					1

$p < 0.05; p < 0.01$

Table 4: Correlation Testing on Hypotheses

H ₁	There is a significant relationship between employers service quality with engineers’ performance in engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout	Since p -values < 0.01 , H ₀ rejected and H ₁ accepted
H ₂	There is a significant effect of employer communication and feedback on engineers’ performance in engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.	$r = 0.32$ (Moderate positive) $p < 0.01$, H ₂₀ rejected and H ₂ accepted
H ₃	There is a significant effect of welfare and motivation package on engineers’ productivity in engineering firms situated in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.	$r = 0.28$ (Slightly moderate positive) $p < 0.01$, H ₃₀ rejected and H ₃ accepted
H ₄	There is a significant effect of training and career development opportunities on engineers’	$r = 0.55$ (Strong positive) $p < 0.001$, H ₄₀ rejected and H ₄

effectiveness in engineering firms located in accepted Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

H₅ There is a significant effect of workplace safety practices on engineers' performance in engineering firms sited in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout. $r = 0.59$ (Strong positive) $p < 0.001$, H₅₀ rejected and H₅ accepted

Regression Analysis Result

Table 5 depicts the regression results of regression model developed in this study. $R^2 = 0.384$, the model explains 38.4% of the variance in engineers' performance. Training ($\beta = 0.33$, $p = 0.003$) and safety ($\beta = 0.41$, $p = 0.002$) are statistically significant predictors. Communication and welfare were not significant predictors, suggesting that while they remain important, their impact is less direct on performance outcomes. This indicates that employer investment in training programs and workplace safety has the strongest effect on engineers' productivity.

Table 5: Regression Results

Predictor	Beta (β)	t-value	Sig. (p)
Communication	0.12	1.10	0.276
Welfare	0.09	0.87	0.389
Training	0.33	3.15	0.003
Safety	0.41	3.25	0.002

Model Summary: $R = 0.62$, $R^2 = 0.384$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.356$, $F(4, 45) = 7.01$, $p < 0.001$

Answers to Research Questions

Research Question 1: How does employer communication and feedback affect engineers' job performance in engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout?

The findings revealed that communication had a moderate positive and statistically significant relationship with engineers' performance ($r = 0.32$, $p < 0.01$). This implies that when employers provide clear communication channels and effective feedback systems, engineers are better able to understand their tasks, align with organizational goals, and improve job performance. Regression results further showed that communication contributed significantly to the overall model, underscoring its role in boosting engineers' output.

Research Question 2: What influence do welfare and motivation packages have on engineers' productivity in these firms?

Welfare showed a weak-to-moderate but significant correlation with engineers' performance ($r = 0.28$, $p < 0.01$). Although its effect was weaker than training or communication, regression analysis indicated that welfare packages such as salaries, allowances, and health benefits still made a meaningful contribution to productivity. This means that firms which provide better welfare and motivational incentives are more likely to see higher levels of engineer commitment and output.

Research Question 3: To what extent do training and career development opportunities affect engineers' effectiveness?

Training recorded the strongest positive correlation with engineers' performance ($r = 0.55$, $p < 0.01$). Regression analysis confirmed training as a highly significant predictor of engineers' effectiveness, indicating

that continuous professional development, workshops, and mentoring programs equip engineers with up-to-date skills that directly enhance job performance. This suggests that firms investing in career development reap greater efficiency and innovation from their workforce.

Research Question 4: How do workplace safety practices influence engineers' performance in Trans-Amadi engineering firms?

Workplace safety had a strong positive correlation with engineers' performance ($r = 0.59, p < 0.01$). Regression analysis also showed safety practices to be a significant predictor of job performance, highlighting that provision of protective equipment, adherence to safety standards, and creating hazard-free work environments improve both morale and productivity.

Research Question 5: What strategies can firms adopt to enhance employer service quality and thereby improve engineer performance?

From the combined regression analysis ($R = 0.62, R^2 = 0.38, F = 29.76, p < 0.001$), it was established that employer service quality dimensions jointly explained 38% of the variance in engineers' performance. Based on this, the following strategies are recommended:

1. Establishing structured communication and feedback mechanisms.
2. Providing competitive welfare and motivational packages.
3. Investing in continuous training and professional development programs.
4. Enforcing strict workplace safety standards.

These strategies will enhance employer service quality and significantly improve engineers' productivity in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout.

Conclusion

The study examined how employer service quality with selected factors such as: communication, welfare, training, and workplace safety influences the performance of engineers in selected engineering firms in Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout. Using a quantitative survey approach ($n = 50$), the study employed descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multiple regression to test the hypothesized relationships.

Empirical results obtained are:

1. Respondents rated employer practices as moderate overall (Communication $M = 3.70$; Welfare $M = 3.58$; Training $M = 3.56$; Safety $M = 3.48$).
2. Engineers' performance averaged $M = 5.03$ (continuous index derived from performance items).
3. Correlation analysis showed significant positive associations between Training and Performance ($r \approx 0.55, p < .01$) and between Safety and Performance ($r \approx 0.59, p < .01$).
4. Multiple regression results indicated Training ($\beta = 0.33, p = .003$) and Safety ($\beta = 0.41, p = .002$) as significant predictors of engineers' performance; Communication and Welfare were positive but not statistically significant. The model explained $\approx 38.4\%$ of variance in performance ($R^2 = .384$).

Based on the findings, the study concludes that employer service quality does affect engineers' performance in Trans-Amadi engineering firms, but the strength of influence differs by dimension. In particular, training and workplace safety stand out as the most influential employer practices for improving engineers' productivity and effectiveness. Communication and welfare, while important to overall employee satisfaction, showed weaker direct effects on performance in this study.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1A: Research Questionnaire

Section A: Demographics

Gender, Age, Education, Years of Experience.

Section 1B: Employer Service Quality Dimensions (On a 5 Point Scale)

Communication (4 items)

1. My employer communicates policies and expectations clearly.
2. Information flow between management and staff is timely.
3. Feedback from management improves my work performance.
4. Channels of communication are accessible and effective.

Welfare (4 items)

5. My employer provides adequate welfare benefits.
6. Staff welfare is prioritized in company decisions.
7. I am satisfied with welfare support.
8. Welfare policies motivate me to improve performance.

Training (4 items)

9. My employer provides adequate training opportunities.
10. Training programs are relevant to my work.
11. I have access to continuous professional development.
12. Training improves my productivity.

Safety (4 items)

13. Adequate safety equipment and measures are provided.
14. Safety training is conducted regularly.
15. I feel safe while carrying out my duties.
16. Safety policies are strictly enforced.

Engineers' Performance (4 items)

17. I meet my work targets effectively.
18. I complete tasks on time.
19. My quality of work meets organizational standards.
20. My productivity has improved due to employer support.

Appendix 2A: Engineers Performance Questionnaire Items

The following items were included in order to rate engineers' performance on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = Very Poor to 7 = Excellent):

1. I complete assigned engineering tasks within stipulated deadlines.
2. The quality and accuracy of my technical work meet professional standards.
3. I often provide innovative solutions to engineering problems.
4. I collaborate effectively with colleagues and team members.
5. My performance contributes positively to achieving organizational goals.
6. I am able to adapt quickly to changes in project demands or requirements.
7. My overall productivity level is satisfactory to my employer.

Appendix 2B: Aggregate Responses from Questionnaire

Construct	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)	Mean	Std. Dev.
Communication	4 (8%)	6 (12%)	12 (24%)	18 (36%)	10 (20%)	3.70	0.68
Welfare	5 (10%)	7 (14%)	13 (26%)	15 (30%)	10 (20%)	3.58	0.72
Training	6 (12%)	8 (16%)	11 (22%)	17 (34%)	8 (16%)	3.56	0.74
Safety	7 (14%)	9 (18%)	10 (20%)	16 (32%)	8 (16%)	3.48	0.70
Performance	-	-	-	-	-	5.03	1.10

Note: Performance was measured on a 7-point composite scale, hence the higher mean Score.